

Economic Dispatch using Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithm

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Abstract – Research has been pertained recently towards nature -inspired algorithms. Many of these algorithms in the past few years were subjected towards Economic dispatch (ED). The bacterial foraging optimization algorithm (BFOA) is considered as a recent heuristic optimization method that mimics how *E. coli* bacterium forages for nutrient, where a mathematical representation for its biological behavior is applied for solving the economic dispatch (ED) in power system, which targets scheduling the power generated to satisfy the needed load in the same time equality and inequality constraints are to be satisfied at minimum fuel cost. This paper presents an overview of foraging of bacteria biology and the steps which simulates this process. Then the BFOA is applied to two systems; a small scale 3 generator system and a large scale 40 generator one. The results obtained show capability of the introduced technique to solve ED problem which is clear in the comparison set with other algorithms.

Keywords: Economic Dispatch, Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithm (BFOA), Chemotaxis.

I. Introduction

ED is non-negligible aspect in modern power systems. Recent researches are directed towards optimization techniques to solve the ED problem. ED targets scheduling the power outputs of generating unit to satisfy demand at the lowest cost where load balance and other system constraints must be satisfied [1], so the ED problem is a highly constrained large-scale optimization problem [2]. The largest percentage of the produced power is from thermal power plants which use fossil-based fuel [3]. Many traditional optimization techniques have been applied to solve ED problem as lambda iteration method, gradient search, linear programming, quadratic programming, dynamic programming and Newton-based methods [4, 5]. These methods show good performance, they fail to achieve success for large scale ED problems especially when non-convex characteristics are taken into consideration [6].

In the past few years, artificial intelligence (AI) [7, 8] based optimization methods are used to solve ED problem, as they are more capable of modeling realistic objective functions. These methods have proved to be capable of solving ED problem compared to classical techniques. Well-known AI based techniques are: particle swarm optimization (PSO) [9, 10], genetic algorithm [11, 12], differential evolution (DE) [13] which yields good and fast solutions while satisfying all the constraints, through using its different crossover strategies. But with the increase in complexity and size of system, DE fails in mapping its entire array of unknown variables together in an efficient way. Firefly algorithm is another self-adaptive algorithm that is applied to solve the ED problem in [14]. In spite of being completely suitable for tuning off its parameters, sometimes it suffers from the getting trapped in local

optimum. Another novel optimization technique is the shuffled frog leaping algorithm (SFLA) [15], it is an evolutionary algorithm which has a significant global search capability, as the shuffling improves sharing information between frogs.

One of the promising methods is the bacterial foraging optimization algorithm (BFOA) which is a heuristic technique that was first introduced by Kevin M. Passino [16] based on the idea of eliminating animals with poor foraging strategies and to favour the ones which have good strategies. BFOA drew attention of researchers in different fields due to its graceful structure. Researchers tried to implement hybrid techniques based on BFOA and other different methods to explore its search capabilities. It has been applied to many objective functions. BFOA was applied successfully to solve different optimization objective functions such as distributed optimization and control [16], harmonic estimation [17], design of optimal power system stabilizers [18] and optimal power flow [19, 20].

In this paper the BFOA is studied as an optimization technique for solving the ED problem, by being tested on small and large scale systems. To check robustness of BFOA it is compared different methods as the Firefly (FA), fuzzy based bacterial foraging algorithm and SFLA.

II. Economic Dispatch

The ED the lowest possible cost subjected to specified constraints [21].

II.1. Fuel Cost Objective

Minimizing total generation cost, mathematically

$$\text{Minimize } F(P_G) = \sum_{i=1}^N F_i(P_{Gi}) \text{ \$/h} \quad (1)$$

In above equation, F_{Gi} (P_{Gi}) is cost function of i^{th} generator which is represented as a quadratic equation that is function in of the power generated, i.e.

$$F_i(P_{Gi}) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i P_{Gi}^2 + b_i P_{Gi} + c_i \quad (2)$$

Where a_i , b_i , c_i are the cost coefficients, N represents generators' number and P_{Gi} is i^{th} generator output..

II.2. Constraints

II.2.1. Generation Capacity Inequality Constraints

Each generator has lower and upper limits for producing power, i.e.

$$P_{Gi}^{\min} \leq P_{Gi} \leq P_{Gi}^{\max} \quad (3)$$

Where, P_{Gi}^{\min} and P_{Gi}^{\max} represents the minimal and the maximal operating outputs of each generator.

II.2.2. Power Balance Equality Constraint

The total generated power must cover the total demand PD and the total transmission losses Ploss. Therefore,

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_G} P_{Gi} - P_D - P_{loss} = 0 \quad (4)$$

The transmission losses are calculated according to B-coefficient matrix [22] using Korn's loss formula [23] as follows,

$$P_L = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N P_{Gi} B_{ij} P_{Gj} + \sum_{i=1}^N B_{0i} P_{Gi} + B_{00} \quad (5)$$

Such that parameters B_{ij} are loss coefficients.

III. Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithm

The BFOA mimics how E coli. Bacteria searches for food. Biological representation of the bacterial foraging, the motion behavior of bacteria and the decision making mechanism are introduced in [24]. The BFOA consists of three main mechanisms, which are Chemotaxis, Reproduction and Elimination- Dispersal. Each of the processes is expressed and followed by the pseudo-code later on.

III.1. Chemotaxis

It represents motion of a single bacterium during the swim and the tumble actions as biologically these are the two possible different directions for the bacteria. It may either start swimming for some time in the same direction or it might go tumbling, and keeps alternating between these two modes of motion during its life. Suppose $\theta^i(j, k, l)$ is the position of i^{th} bacterium at the j^{th} step, during the k^{th} reproduction process and l^{th} elimination-dispersal step. Let $C(i)$ be the size of a step moved by bacteria in a random direction. Mathematically the chemotaxis step of bacterium is represented as,

$$\theta^i(j + 1, k, l) = \theta^i(j, k, l) + C(i) \frac{\Delta(i)}{\sqrt{\Delta^T(i)\Delta(i)}} \quad (6)$$

Where Δ indicates a vector in a random direction whose elements lie in $[-1,1]$

III.2. Reproduction

Eventually bacteria with worst health die, while bacteria with good health split into two that are located in the same position. As a result to that the population size remains constant.

III.3. Elimination and dispersal

Changes in the environment could be either gradually or suddenly affects the bacterium population. These changes result from various causes, e.g. high temperature. Such events may lead to the death of the whole population or disperse into a new location. This is simulated in the BFOA via liquidating some bacteria randomly with a small probability, while disperse in initialized randomly in the search space.

IV. Steps of BFOA Implementation

The BFOA is applied to solve ED problem through a series of steps which are mentioned below. They are also represented in the flowchart of Fig 1 [25].

- Initialize parameters $p, S, N_s, N_c, N_{re}, P_{ed}, N_{ed}$
 $C(i)$ ($I = 1, 2, 3, \dots, S$), θ^i
Where p : Search space dimensions, S : Number of Bacterium, N_s : Swim steps, N_c : Chemotactic steps, N_{re} : Reproductive steps, P_{ed} : Probability of elimination, N_{ed} : Elimination and dispersal steps, $C(i)$: Run length unit
- Initialize Elimination-dispersal loop: $l=l+1$
- Start reproduction loop: $k=k+1$
- Initialize Chemotaxis loop: $j=j+1$.
- Count a step and calculate the fitness, save the value obtained, compare this value to the value obtained before this step. Keep continuing until the number of chemotactic steps is finished.
- If $j < N_c$, return to 4 and continue moving.
- Reproduction
 - For each bacterium, let
 - $J_{\text{health}}^i = \sum_{j=1}^{N_c+1} J(i, j, k, l)$ (7)
is bacteria's health. Then they are sorted ascending according to (J_{health}).
- Bacteria are divided into 2 S_r , where S_r bacteria with high J_{health} die, and the other S_r split at the same locations as their parents.
- If $k < N_{re}$ then return to 2 and start generating the next step in chemotactic loop until the number of reproduction steps is fulfilled.

- Elimination-dispersal event: each bacterium is eliminated and dispersed randomly with probability P_{ed} , such that the population is kept constant. If $l < N_{ed}$, go to 2, otherwise, end [26].

Fig. 1 Flowchart of BFOA

V. Simulation Results and Analysis

Two test cases are studied using the proposed approach for 3 and 40 generators systems. The test cases are analyzed and compared with other ED methods.

V.1. Test Case I

A three generators system is used to verify the BFOA method, the coefficients and generator limits are given in Table 1 [27]. The system is tested at load demand of 450 MW. The BFOA parameters are adjusted to $S = 10$, $N_c = 25$, $N_s = 4$, $N_{re} = 4$, $N_{ed} = 2$, $P_{ed} = 0.25$, $C = 0.05$. The results obtained for five different trials are shown in Table 2.

TABLE I
COEFFICIENTS AND GENERATOR LIMITS OF 3 GENERATORS SYSTEM

Gen No.	Pmin	Pmax	a	b	c
1	100	600	0.001562	7.92	561
2	100	400	0.001940	7.85	310
3	50	200	0.004820	7.97	78

TABLE II
RESULTS OF THREE GENERATORS SYSTEM

Demand (MW)	1st Run	2nd Run	3rd Run	4th Run	5thRun
P1	205.922	205.31	208.17	205.32	207.12
P2	182.582	183.30	179.78	183.31	181.28
P3	61.497	61.39	62.05	61.37	61.59
Cost (\$/hr)	4652.43	4652.43	4652.47	4652.43	4652.44

A graphical representation for the final result obtained in each of the 5 trials for the 3-generator system is shown in figures (2-6), as every time the program is run, the bacteria are scattered in the search space in different locations representing various values for generator output, then they swim or tumble towards the best cost value for the objective function. It can be noticed that in each of the figures each bacterium has a different location in each run, but are all surrounding the location of the optimum solution which at least one bacterium has reached

Fig. 2. 1st Run

Fig. 3 2nd Run

Fig. 4: 3rd Run

Figure 5: 4th Run

Fig. 6: 5th Run

The best results obtained for generators' output in Test case 1 which are found in the 4th run are compared to Firefly algorithm (FA) [27] and shuffled frog leaping algorithm (SFLA) [28] in Table 3. The comparison shows close results to both algorithms.

TABLE 3
BFOA COMPARISON TO FA

Demand (MW)	FA [27]	SFLA [28]	BFOA
P1 (MW)	205.1	205.31	205.32
P2 (MW)	183.7	183.35	183.31
P3 (MW)	61.2	61.35	61.37
Cost (\$/hr)	4652	4652.4	4652.43

V.2. Test Case II

A 40-unit system is tested using the introduced algorithm which serves a demand of 10500 MW, the generator's data are given in [29]. The BFOA parameters are adjusted at $S = 40$, $N_c=400$, $N_s=4$, $N_{re}=4$, $N_{ed}=2$, $P_{ed}=0.25$, $C=0.05$. The data in Table 4 represents the minimum values conducted for 20 independent trials where each run is initialized with various random solutions.

TABLE 4
RESULTS OF 40- GENERATOR SYSTEM

Unit (MW)	BFOA		
P1	113.9438	P21	499.8787
P2	113.9984	P22	549.0531
P3	119.9988	P23	525.87
P4	186.5511	P24	502.6751
P5	88.75929	P25	515.1173
P6	132.8726	P26	500.3124
P7	288.1802	P27	11.29289
P8	292.0695	P28	11.78528
P9	297.8057	P29	14.73487
P10	149.8406	P30	96.89315
P11	240.2732	P33	186.1218
P12	212.3551	P32	189.0222
P13	281.4568	P33	189.9974
P14	360.1448	P34	198.6604
P15	313.3916	P35	197.9063
P16	330.2379	P36	195.5059
P17	472.8097	P37	109.8013
P18	447.7516	P38	107.588
P19	438.9058	P39	105.7941
P20	467.2548	P40	443.3885
Cost (\$/h)	121025.079		

The value of the minimum fuel cost for Test case II found by the BFOA is 121025.079 \$/h. By comparing this value to the best fuel cost obtained using fuzzy based bacterial foraging algorithm by P.K. Hota in [30] which is 121,415.653 \$/h, we observe that the BFOA has shown better performance.

As number of generators represents the number of dimensions, it is not possible to represent all the dimensions of the 40-generator system, so generators are chosen randomly which are divided into groups of 3 generators to be represented graphically in Fig. 7-11.

Fig. 7: Results for generators 1, 3 and 5

Fig. 11. Results for generators 30, 34 and 38

Fig. 8: Results for generators 9, 11 and 13

Fig. 9: Results for generators 15, 18 and 19

Fig. 10 Results for generators 22, 24, and 28.

VI. Conclusion

This paper proposes BFOA for solving economic dispatch problem. It is tested using two systems of 3 and 40 generators, where it succeeded in meeting the required load while keeping the equality and inequality constraints satisfied at the same time even for large scale system. The results obtained from the comparison of the proposed algorithm to that of FA, SFLA and fuzzy based bacterial foraging algorithm show the good performance of the BFOA which proved to be a reliable and a promising algorithm for solving the ED problem.

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